

Ligand Substitution Kinetics as a Tool for Analysis of Multicomponent Mixtures Relevant to Environmental and Geochemical Problems

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This paper provides a brief review of the principles of kinetic methods of analysis followed by a more detailed review of recent achievements in applications of ligand substitution kinetics to determination of mixtures of interest in natural water chemistry. The most successful methods in the literature are methods which prepare, in advance, a group of metal ions or a group of ligands in complexes favourable for kinetic analysis and determine rate constants separately for each. This does not address the most interesting problem, use of kinetic differences to recognize the species present in a raw natural water sample. The problem is that the rate constant (which is the analog of a spectroscopic frequency) must be extracted from the data making the analysis both qualitative and quantitative. Progress on this difficult matter is reviewed including model studies and previously unpublished work from this laboratory.

(A) INTRODUCTION

IN contrast to most of the analytical techniques which involve equilibrium measurements of a particular parameter; kinetic methods of analysis are based upon dynamic measurements of the rate of the chemical reaction. The attractive aspects of kinetic methods include good sensitivity (extreme sensitivity in the case of catalytic species), a means of economical instrumentation, and often improved speed compared to other techniques. But, most important to this paper, kinetic methods are capable of differentiating between closely related components of mixtures by measuring the difference of reaction rates of the components with a common reagent. Consequently, under suitable conditions, kinetic methods can be applied to determine simultaneously the concentrations of the various compounds present in a multicomponent system. The rate constant becomes a parameter of qualitative analysis. It is worth noting as more than a crude metaphor that first order rate constants have dimensions of frequency and that differentiation of components on the basis of kinetics is "kinetic spectrometry".

(B) KINETIC METHODS OF ANALYSIS.

(i) Catalytic Kinetics.

Generally, kinetic methods are classified into two categories: (a) catalysed reaction, and (b) uncatalysed reactions^{1,2,3}. In a catalysed reaction, the catalyst can either accelerate or retard the rate of a particular reaction by altering the activation energy or the kinetic order without changing the point of equilibrium. Consider the following reaction,

where C is the catalyst, S the substrate, X is the intermediate catalyst complex, and R is a reagent molecule that reacts with X to yield the product P with the elimination of a molecule Z. The total reaction rate is the sum of the rates of the catalysed reaction (1) and (2) and the uncatalysed reaction (3), i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} (\text{total}) &= \frac{dx}{dt} (\text{cat}) + \frac{dx}{dt} (\text{uncat}) \\ &= K\alpha_c [C]_0 ([R]_0 - x) + k_3 [S]_0 ([R]_0 - x) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The term K is a composite constant of all the rate constants and equilibrium constants and α_c is the product concentration or a more complex function of all the concentrations of the components participating in the reaction except $[C]_0$ which is the original concentration of the catalyst. The term $[R]_0$ is the initial concentration of the species which changes in concentration in the course of the reaction and $([R]_0 - x)$ is the observed concentration of $[R]$ at any time, t, after the reaction has begun. $[S]_0$ is the initial concentration of the substrate. Experimentally, the concentration $[S]_0$ is often kept in large excess such that α_c and $[S]_0$ can be considered to be constant throughout the experiment. If $([R]_0 - x)$ approximates $[R]_0$, equation (4) reduces to the following differential equation,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} (\text{total}) = F [C]_0 + F' \quad (5)$$

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where F' is the rate of the uncatalysed reaction (3). The equivalent integrated form of the equation is obtained by integrating expression (4),

$$\ln \left(\frac{[R]_1}{[R]_2} \right) = (F [C]_0 + F')(t_2 - t_1) \quad (6)$$

The determination of the catalyst concentration is normally based on treating the experimental kinetic data with either one of the last two kinetic expressions. In equation (5), which is simpler to interpret than equation (6), the factor F is generally much larger than 1. It corresponds to an amplification factor and highlights one of the unique features of catalytic methods: catalytic methods use chemical (as opposed to electronic) methods of signal amplification.

(ii) *Uncatalysed Kinetics.*

Using kinetic methods for uncatalysed reactions, both single component analysis and kinetic spectrometry are possible². For a single species A to be determined, A may be in excess such that its concentration does not change in the course of reaction. If R is the other reagent and X is the product of the reaction, the pseudo-first order kinetic expression is :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_A ([R]_0 - x) [A]_0 \quad (7)$$

Both the differential and integrated forms of the equation can be used in the determination of an unknown concentration of A . The techniques involved are the same as described in the case of a catalytic reaction.

Kinetic spectrometry is based on differential rate methods^{2,4} in which differentiation of two or more chemical species is possible without prior separation. Consider the following reactions where A, B, \dots, N are the reactive components of a mixture and R a common reagent present in large excess, i.e., $[R]_0 \gg [A]_0 + [B]_0 + \dots + [N]_0$. Assume that R reacts with A, N by pseudo first order processes.

The concentration of the product p at any time t is :

$$\begin{aligned} [P]_t = & [A]_0 (1 - e^{-k_A t}) + [B]_0 (1 - e^{-k_B t}) + \\ & + [N]_0 (1 - e^{-k_N t}) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $[A]_0, [B]_0, \dots, [N]_0$ are the initial concentrations of the species. Experimentally, the change of $[P]_t$ is normally monitored by observing parameters such as absorbance, conductivity, or fluorescence. In terms of

absorbance changes, equation (9) can be rewritten as :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Abs}_{(P)_t} = & \epsilon [A]_0 (1 - e^{-k_A t}) + \epsilon [B]_0 (1 - e^{-k_B t}) + \\ & + \epsilon [N]_0 (1 - e^{-k_N t}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient of the product P and l is the pathlength.

There are a number of ways of treating the kinetic data with equation (9) depending on the circumstances. In the simplest case of a binary mixture of A & B in which the rate of reaction of component A is larger than that of B , the Logarithmic Extrapolation Method is often used. Equation (9) becomes for late time values :

$$\ln([P]_\infty - [P]_t) = -k_B t + \ln [B]_0 \quad (11)$$

A plot of $\ln \{ [P]_\infty - [P]_t \}$ against t will yield a straight line with a slope of $-k_B$ and an intercept equal to $\ln [B]_0$. The value of $[A]_0$ can be obtained by subtracting $[B]_0$ from the total initial concentration of the mixture. Note that the independent values of k_A and k_B are not necessary in this graphical computation method.

The first order Single Point Method developed by Kolthoff and Lee² is based on the total concentration of the mixture after a single fixed time interval. The method is only applicable strictly for binary mixtures. If equation (9) is divided by $[P]_\infty$ or $[A]_0 + [B]_0$, it can be rearranged to :

$$\frac{[P]_\infty - [P]_t}{[P]_\infty} = \left(e^{-k_A t} - e^{-k_B t} \right) \frac{[A]_0}{[A]_0 + [B]_0} + e^{-k_B t} \quad (12)$$

A calibration curve can be obtained by plotting $[P]_\infty - [P]_t / [P]_\infty$ versus the initial mole fraction of A in the mixture. The slope of the curve is $(e^{-k_A t} - e^{-k_B t})$ and the intercept $e^{-k_B t}$ and $e^{-k_A t}$ at mole fraction of A equal to zero and unity.

A third graphical method for treating pseudo-first order reactions of binary mixtures is the Tangent Method. By differentiating equation (9), one obtains,

$$-\frac{d([P]_\infty - [P]_t)}{dt} = k_A [A]_t + k_B [B]_t \quad (13)$$

As the faster reacting component A diminishes in concentration, equation (13) becomes

$$-\frac{d([P]_\infty - [P]_t)}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{[P]_\infty - [P]_t} \right) [A]_t \rightarrow 0 = k_B \quad (14)$$

Therefore, for a plot of $([P]_\infty - [P]_t)$ versus t , as $[A]_t$ approaches zero, the tangents of the plot approach a constant that equals k_B .

Finally, the most versatile method that is truly capable of multicomponent analysis, is the Method of

Proportional Equations. Using equation (10) directly, a series of similar equations can be established by measuring the absorbance of the product (or any parameter which changes proportionally with the reactions) at various time intervals, e. g. Abs (P_{t_1}), Abs (P_{t_2}), ...

Abs (P_{t_n}). Theoretically, any number n of chemical species can be determined by setting up at least the equivalent number n of simultaneous equations and solving them. This technique using proportional equations is also applicable in cases of reactions that are pseudo-first or first order in reagent, i. e. $[R]_0 \ll ([A]_0 + [B]_0)$.

For situations where second order kinetics arise, i. e. $[R]_0 \neq ([A]_0 + [B]_0)$, a number of methods can be used to resolve the kinetic data. The details of these techniques will not be given here^{2,3}.

From the discussion above, it is obvious that catalytic kinetic methods with chemical amplification are very sensitive and have very low detection limits for the elements being sought. However, they are not practical if applied in the case of multicomponent analysis. In this respect, despite the lower sensitivity generally associated with direct kinetic methods, these will be useful in speciation studies. Simultaneous kinetic determinations of binary mixtures and multicomponent mixtures have been reported using differential rate methods. Of particular interest to inorganic chemists and environmentalists are a series of studies reported by Margerum *et al* including the simultaneous determination of components of mixtures of metallic elements^{5,6} and aminopolycarboxylic acids⁷, by kinetic analysis, and trace metal analysis via coordination chain reactions^{8,9,10}.

(C) SUBSTITUTION REACTIONS IN KINETIC ANALYSIS

Consider the metal complex ML in solution, there are three simple types of reaction possible :

All can be used analytically.

Margerum *et al*^{5,6} in two separate studies reported quantitative analyses of mixtures of metal ions using a stopped-flow kinetic method based on the following reaction scheme :

where $MCyDTA^{2-}$ is the divalent metal complex of *trans*-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N, N, N', N'-tetraacetate and M'^{2+} is a divalent metal ion different from M used as a scavenger (in the two studies reported, Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} were used). The metal ions being sought, M, were first converted into their respective $MCyDTA$ complexes and then reacted with a reagent solution containing at least a 10 fold excess of the scavenger M' , an ionic strength adjuster, and acid for the desired pH of the reaction. Direct electrophilic substitution of M by M' is not possible because the ligand CyDTA forms a coordination cage which cannot accommodate more than one metal at a time. Only acid assistance will lead to the dissociation of the $MCyDTA$ complex. The subsequent reaction between $HCyDTA^{3-}$ and M'^{2+} is fast compared to the acid hydrolysis, thus making reaction (18) the rate determining step. The appearance of $M'CyDTA^{2-}$ is followed as a monitor of the progress of the reaction. From a kinetic trace of the absorbance change of $M'CyDTA$ versus time, equations similar to expression (10) were set up and solved simultaneously. For a binary mixture of only Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , graphical methods could be used to treat the experimental kinetic data; but details of kinetic data processing by on-line regression analysis for several components were reported in a separate paper¹¹. A prior knowledge of the values of the rate constants k_A, k_B, \dots, k_N is not absolutely necessary in order to solve equation (10) nongraphically provided that sufficient data are available from each kinetic run for the appropriate computer curve fitting. The disadvantages of this approach include poorer accuracy due to the presence of more variables for fitting and increasing computer cost. Thus the rate constants are elucidated individually in separate experiments by running the pure $MCyDTA$ components under the same reaction conditions.

In the two studies reported, Margerum *et al* applied the method to analyse mixtures of alkaline earth, transition, and lanthanide metal ions (2 - 4 components) with good success. Both the accuracy and precision are within $\pm(5-10)\%$, and sensitivity was reported to be as low as 10^{-6} M metal ion. The power of resolution is dependent upon the rate constant ratios between the metal ions to be separated. In the case of alkaline earths, very small concentrations of a species can be determined in the presence of 10 - 100 fold excess of most other metals. To improve resolution between metal ions with close ratios of rate constants, kinetic degeneracy can be removed by either changing the pH, temperature or other physical parameters of the reaction. With proper automated data handling, the technique offers very rapid analyses of mixtures of metal ions. The practical application of the method was tested by analyzing the contents of alkaline-earth metal ions in sea water, dolomite, and blood serum. The determinations of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} concentrations

by the kinetic method compared favourably with analyses done by standard methods such as atomic absorption and EDTA titrations.

Kloosterboer^{1,2} in a later study reported a slight modification of the CyDTA-kinetic method. Instead of conducting the kinetic runs under constant pH conditions (kinetic runs performed by Margerum and his coworkers were buffered either by acetate at pH levels below 7 or borate-manitol for pH levels above 7), a continuous pH variation method was chosen (high pH → low pH). Consequently, reaction (19) becomes truly second-order rather than pseudo-first order. The decay curve for MCyDTA is then an S-shape curve rather than exponential for a single metal species. The absorbance of M'Cy against time increases rapidly at first as [H⁺] increases, however, as time increases, [MCyDTA] decreases and absorbance levels off.

The type of double ligand-exchange reaction expressed in equation (16) is sometimes called coordination chain reaction because the exchange is often initiated by the presence of trace amounts of either of the ligands, and in the chain-propagation steps one multidentate ligand displaces the other from its metal complex and vice versa. A series of studies by Margerum *et al.*^{8,9,10} involving the following reaction

(EDTA = ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, Trien = triethylenediamine) had demonstrated the catalytic effect of trace amount of free ligands and the inhibiting effect of free metal ions on the rate of ligand-exchange. A later study by Stara and Kopanica¹⁸ using a similar ligand exchange reaction,

(TTHA = triethylenetetraminehexacetic acid,

Tetren = triethylenetetramine)

displayed similar behaviour. Trace metal determinations can be achieved either by a kinetic titration in which the reaction rate in (21) will increase after all the metal is complexed by TTHA, or using a fixed time procedure described earlier in catalytic kinetics. Accuracy of such analysis are expected to be within ±7% and depending on the mode in which the rate is monitored, the sensitivity level ranges from 10⁻⁶M to 10⁻⁸M.

Gamon and Reilley¹⁴, in a discussion of the kinetic analysis of mixtures by the method of proportional equations, reported an analysis for gallium based on the following nucleophilic substitution reaction :

(Erio R = Eriochrome Blue Black or Calcon)

It was possible to determine the concentration of [Ga³⁺] in a mixture of other metal ions ; selectivity of the method was achieved kinetically. The Erio R complexes of most other metals react very rapidly within the first minute after mixing. On the other hand, the Ga dye complex reacts quite slowly, only approximately 1% in 12 minutes. Therefore, the absorbance change of [Ga-Erio R] at 568 nm was followed during the time interval of 1 to 12 minutes.

Separation of mixtures of some heavy metals by differential kinetic analysis using ligand substitution reactions was reported by Tanaka *et al.*¹⁵. The metal ions were first converted into their corresponding ethyleneglycol bis(2-amino-ethylether) N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (EGTA) complex and subsequently reacted with another ligand 4-(2-pyridylazo)-resorcinol (PAR).

For the PAR complexes of Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), and Pb(II), the spectral characteristics are very similar in that the absorption maxima all occur in the wavelength range from 490-520 nm. These authors were able to take advantage of this by monitoring the appearance of the various metal-PAR complexes at an intermediate wavelength (e.g. 495 nm chosen by these authors) where a "approximately common" product is monitored. In the case of two component analysis, data were processed graphically. A ratio of the two pseudo-first order rate constants of the two reacting components greater than 6 led to good resolution. Both the forward and the reverse reactions of the equilibrium expressed in equation (23) are applicable in analysis of the metal listed. Under the first set of conditions (i.e. [M²⁺] = 1-3 × 10⁻⁶M ; [PAR] = 1-3 × 10⁻⁴M ; [EGTA] = 5.5 × 10⁻⁶M ; pH = 8-9 ; 25°C ; μ = 0.1), the equilibrium is much favoured to the right for Co(II) and Ni(II) so that the reverse reaction can be neglected in the kinetic treatment. Under identical conditions, the opposite is true for Pb(II) and Zn(II). In the case of copper, neither the forward nor the reverse reaction proceeds to completion. If the conditions were changed (i.e. [EGTA] = 5 × 10⁻⁴M ; pH = 8.5), the reverse reaction would be favoured for the copper complex so that the forward reaction can be neglected. It can be shown that the reaction system chosen can achieve excellent resolution provided that the proper conditions are selected and recognizing the correct state of the equilibrium. Most analyses were within ±5% accuracy and detection levels down to the 10⁻⁶M region. The technique is also relatively free from interferences from other ions.

In a similar study, Yatsimirskii¹⁶ and his co-workers were able to analyze mixtures of rare earth ions kinetically with stopped-flow spectrophotometry. The system is based on

where Ln is a rare earth ion, X is the Xylenol Orange anion, and EDTA is ethylenediaminetetracetate. Only

two components analyses were reported. The rare earth ions were analysed as their highly coloured Xylenol Orange complexes. Progress of the parallel reactions was monitored at 540 nm, λ_{\max} of the LnX complexes. Kinetic runs were conducted at 25° in a medium which was buffered (pH=4.75) and ionic strength adjusted (0.1M) by acetate. Two graphical methods were presented to treat the kinetic data depending on the ratio between the pseudo-first order rate constants of the two reacting rare earth components. In the case of the Praseodymium (Pr) and Ytterbium (Yb) dye complexes, the rate constants were 160 sec⁻¹ and 30 sec⁻¹ respectively. Under conditions where $k_1 : k_2 \geq 3$, the authors used a simple extrapolation method. The slower component of the kinetic curve was extrapolated to t=0, and the initial concentration of [Yb]₀ was determined from the absorbance reading of [YbX] at t=0. When $k_1 : k_2 \leq 3$, as in the case of a mixture of Lanthanum (La) and Samarium (Sa) dye complexes for which the corresponding rate constants were 150 sec⁻¹ and 105 sec⁻¹, an initial rate method was used. Quantitative determinations of mixtures of Pr and Yb, and La and Sa were reported to be within ±15%. The sensitivity levels reported were generally around 10⁻⁴M.

Coombs, Vasiliades and Margerum⁷ reported an analysis of mixtures of aminopolycarboxylic acids by the ligand substitution kinetic method. The simultaneous kinetic determination was based on the conversion of the aminopolycarboxylic acids, Lⁿ⁻, to their respective Ni²⁺ complexes and the observation of the rate of reaction of the Ni²⁺ aminopolycarboxylates with CN⁻ to yield a common product, tetracyanonickelate (rate determining step).

Data treatment was identical to that reported in references (5), (6), and (11). The first set of experiments involved a single component determination of NTA (nitrilotriacetic acid) in EDTA. The accuracies of the analyses performed at the two wavelengths 267 nm and 285 nm were ±4% and ±6% for a range of NiNTA⁻ concentrations studied. By using a high initial concentration of NiEDTA²⁻, it was possible to determine as low as 0.001 mole % of NiNTA⁻. It was remarked by these authors that single component analysis of a large variety of Ni(II)-aminopolycarboxylates could be performed using the intercept or extrapolation method if the ratio of the rate constants between components was large. Simultaneous determinations of 2-component (NiEDDA + NiNTA⁻) mixture, 3-component (NiEDDA + NiNTA⁻ + NiEGTA²⁻) mixture, and a 4-component (EGT + HPDTA + HEEDTA + EDTA) mixture were performed and the resulting data computer processed.¹¹ (EDDA = ethylene-diamine-N,N'-diacetic acid, EGTA = ethylene glycol bis (aminoethyl) tetraacetic acid, HPDTA = 1, 3- diamino - 2 - hydroxy propanetetraacetic acid, HEEDTA = N-hydroxy-ethylethylenediaminetetraacetic acid). For the two component analysis, the accuracy was generally within ±5%.

In a three component system, the results were only fair, but still support the feasibility of tertiary mixture analysis. For the four component analysis, the results were good for the major components (EGTA, HEEDTA), but poor for the minor (HPDTA, EDTA) components. Part of the difficulty arose from the fact that the rate constants for EGTA and HPDTA were very close to each other. Remaining error was attributed to interferences due to mixed CN⁻ complexes. In the presence of Fe³⁺, the determination was performed only after Fe³⁺ was precipitated and filtered off at pH=8.5. The single component kinetic method was applied to analyze for NTA in natural water samples. The sample was treated with excess Ni(ClO₄)₂ and pH adjusted to 11. Excess nickel was kept in solution by using ammonia as a masking agent. The authors claimed a sensitivity level of 10 ppb and accuracy to within 10-15% with the present method.

(D) METAL COMPLEXES IN AQUATIC SYSTEMS

The limit of the achievements described in the previous section is that the sample components had to be converted to favourable forms prior to the application of multicomponent kinetic analysis (kinetic spectrometry). Moreover, the rate constants were often evaluated independently for each of the components in advance. This suppresses the opportunity to use rate constants as qualitative parameters to help to identify the species present in natural waters.

The species present in raw natural water samples are an increasingly urgent problem. Approaches include use of ultrafiltration, electrochemistry, and kinetics¹⁷⁻²⁷. This is the most challenging application of kinetics because both rate constants and concentrations must be extracted from the kinetic data. Without some advance in technique this dual requirement will degrade the accuracy described for methods considered in section (C). But, the problem is important enough to warrant accepting the challenge. The two metal ions of specific kinetic interest have been Fe³⁺ and Cu²⁺ to this date.

The cautious approach to the difficulties indicated is to begin with relatively simple model systems. In this laboratory, we have attempted to develop methods for study of Fe(III) species using kinetic techniques. The choice of Fe(III) was dictated by the convenient rates of reaction of Fe(OH₂)₃³⁺ and Fe(OH₂)₂OH²⁺ with complex forming reagents with respect to the stopped-flow kinetic technique. Sulfosalicylic acid (SSA) was chosen as a complexing agent which forms an easily detectable species. Use of excess SSA (10⁻²M) in solutions with excess protons (pH=1 to 2) as a reagent which could be mixed with aqueous samples containing Fe(III) species created a situation where the reactions being monitored approached monomeric Fe(III)-SSA species as a common product. Also, the pH of the mixture and its ionic strength are controlled by the SSA and acid solution so that rates will not be influenced significantly by constituents of the dilute aqueous solutions which form the sample. The method is sensitive to Fe(III) to levels just below 1 × 10⁻⁶M.

This corresponds to values just below one ppm. One ppm is a factor of ten higher than "dissolved iron" values for a majority of interesting natural waters.

So far, model systems examined have included studies of binding in acid solution (where Fe(III) is monomeric) of Fe(III) by a well characterized fulvic acid supplied by the Soil Research Institute of Agriculture, Canada¹⁸ and by the biochemically widely distributed sulphur donor ligand, glutathione¹⁹. In each case the mixture examined had only two components, free Fe(III) and the complex. The conditional equilibrium constants for Fe(III) binding were extracted as a function of pH.

We are now extending these studies to solutions at higher and more geochemically relevant pH values (≥ 4). The Fe(III) species present in water at $pH \geq 4$, are expected to be polymeric or colloidal. Sommer and Margerum²¹ have examined the kinetics of rapid acid decomposition of the simplest Fe(III) polymer, $Fe_2(OH)_2^{3+}$ by stopped-flow. A polymeric species identified by Spiro *et al.*²⁷ has been examined kinetically by Sommer *et al.*²². In HNO_3 , acid hydrolysis of polymeric Fe(III) is very much slower than acid dissociation of dimeric $Fe_2(OH)_2^{3+}$. We find that dilute Fe(III) solutions near $pH=4$ contain components that react with SSA at rates similar to the polymeric Fe(III) species of Sommer *et al.*²². These solutions also contain fast reacting components related to monomeric Fe(III)^{18,19,21} and very slowly reacting components which relate to filterable, but not readily settleable, particulates²³. These model studies have not yet solved general problems of Fe(III) in natural water. But, they do point in a definite direction. The pH dependence of Fe(III) binding in solutions where Fe(III) is monomeric^{18,19} is non-simple. $Fe(OH)_2^{3+}$ is a stronger acid than many ligands. This results in competition between hydrolysis and ligation as the basis of Fe(III) chemistry in natural water. If Fe(III) and ligands are mixed at intermediate pH, a complex mixture of Fe(III) polymers and Fe(III) complexes are formed. The result is most promising for kinetic techniques because the very variety of these species makes it clear that *rate differences* between significant species *can be large* in natural systems.

Differences of species among monomeric Fe(III) entities, Fe(III) bond to organic polyelectrolytes, like fulvic acid, and Fe(III) in hydrolytic polymers approaching precipitation at the colloidal level are kinetically significant. Thus, the kinetic technique is very powerful and nature has supplied us the initiative to expand the method. In the most interesting circumstances, like natural water, a variety of species arise which differentiate over many orders of magnitude kinetically²³. The needed additional resolutions of the approach is provided by nature. The only problem that must be solved is adequate sensitivity. Quite possibly, fluorescence detection can provide the desired increase in sensitivity.

The speciation of Cu^{2+} in natural water (both sea water and fresh water) is also of considerable interest to

the environmentalist because of the toxicity of the metal. In a report by Odier and Plichon²⁴, the chemical forms of Cu^{2+} in sea water were determined by superimposed sinusoidal-voltage polarography. The displacement of the half-wave potential of reduction of Cu(II) was dependent on the nature of the Cu(II) complex(es) present and the pH of the sea water. The conclusion was that Cu^{2+} in sea water is present predominantly as $Cu^{2+}(aq)$, $CuCl^+$, and $Cu(HCO_3)_2(OH)^-$. Another study by Shuman and his coworkers²⁵ used anodic stripping voltammetry (ASV) to establish the conditional formation constants²³ of trace metal complexes present in water. The method was based on data obtained from a complexometric titration monitored by ASV. The titration curve was obtained by adding successive aliquots of metal to the sample containing "organic ligands"; the appropriate stripping currents which reflected only the concentration of "free" or unassociated metal ion were recorded. The endpoint of this titration of ligand with metal is an estimate of total free ligand concentration or complexing power of the water under study. The composition and concentrations of "bound" metal complexes are inferred from the conditional formation constants. A very detailed study of chemical species of copper was reported by Stiff²⁶. Assorted analytical techniques including kinetics were employed to elucidate the various forms. Copper present as Cu^{2+} was determined by a cupric-ion selective electrode. Copper complexed by carbonate according to equation (27)

was determined from the thermodynamic equilibrium constant of $CuCO_3$. This reflects the high kinetic lability which guarantees that equilibrium will be achieved in all cases. The concentration of free $[Cu^{2+}]$ and $[H^+]$ can be determined by the appropriate selective electrodes. Bicarbonate concentration $[HCO_3^-]$ was obtained by titration because it is not a minor component. The values of activity coefficients were obtained from the literature. Cyanide complexes, $Cu(CN)_2^-$, which are very stable ($K=10^{22}$) in solution were determined as the difference between total copper concentration determined with neocuproine, after nitric acid digestion, and copper concentration determined with PHTTT (3-propyl-5-hydroxy-5-D-arabino-tetrahydroxy-butyl-3-thiazolidine-2-thione). Kinetics of formation of CuPHTTT was monitored. This method of analysis was designed to take advantage of the fact that cyanide quantitatively inhibited the formation of the copper-PHTTT complex formation. Copper complexed by humic substances (humic or fulvic acid) was determined both by extraction with hexanol and by kinetic monitoring of substitution of the humate by PHTTT to form the corresponding complex. Copper that was complexed by amino acids and polypeptides was assumed to be given by equation (28),

The variety of methods used by Stiff underline the complexity of the species problem. Kinetic methods appeared useful in a middle ground between very labile species which are easily described by equilibrium modeling and very non-labile species which are hard to detect unless the sample is subjected to severe treatment. It is obvious that most dissolved metals are likely to be coordinated to the large number of naturally occurring dissolved ligands, e. g. HCO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , pyrophosphates, humic substances, amino acids and etc. However, under any given set of conditions, the metal is usually present in a few predominant forms that will differentiate sharply on the scale of kinetic lability.

(E) THE FUTURE OF KINETIC ANALYSIS IN SPECIATION STUDIES.

With exception of certain electrochemical techniques, most present analytical methods aggregate various species of metals to total bulk concentration. In this respect, kinetic spectrometry described in this paper is an attractive alternative to electrochemical methods. The simultaneous multicomponent determination studies reported by Margerum *et al.*^{5,6,7} fully demonstrate the potential of kinetics when rate constant differences can be suitably managed. Nature often suitably manages rate constant²⁸.

The main limitation of our work in kinetic spectrometry has been sensitivity. To increase the potential and versatility of kinetic spectrometry, a simple stopped-flow fluorescence instrument has been developed in this laboratory for incorporation of the advantages of the stopped-flow technique into the widely available Aminco-Bowman spectrofluorimeter. The choice of fluorimetry as the monitoring mode has two great advantages. (1) For reactions that are already kinetically within the stopped-flow time scale or are slower, fluorimetry can greatly enhance the sensitivity of the method, this will possibly bring the detection level down to the low $10^{-9}M$ levels which were previously reserved for catalytic methods. (2) For reactions that are too fast for stopped-flow experiments, the high sensitivity of fluorimetry would enable use of much lower initial reactant concentrations and hence bring the overall reaction rate down to the stopped-flow range. It is expected that metal species present in concentrations of $10^{-9}M$ can be determined routinely with this method. Certainly appropriate reagents for Al^{3+} analysis via fluorescence exist²⁹. Currently, work is being conducted in this laboratory on three fronts, (i) the speciation of Cu^{2+} ion using 1,1,3-Tricyano-2-Amino-1-Propene (Triap) as a fluorescent reagent, (ii) the speciation of various hydroxo-complexes of Al^{3+} in natural water, and (iii) determination of the various forms of Fe^{3+} in aqueous solution including the hydroxo-complexes present at various pH. In this last context, we should add that kinetic methods allow for simultaneous handling of monomeric ions, polymers, colloids, and poorly settleable suspended particulates. This probably centres on the key question in natural water chemistry, "What is in the larger entities?"

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